

METHANE AND CARBON DIOXIDE AFFECTS AIR QUALITY. GREENHOUSE GASES IN THE ATMOSPHERE.

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The Global Greenhouse Gas Reference Network measures the atmospheric distribution and trends of the three main long-term drivers of climate change, carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide (N₂O), as well as carbon monoxide (CO) which is an important indicator of air pollution.

Energy from the Sun that makes its way to Earth can have trouble finding its way back out to space. The greenhouse effect causes some of this energy to be waylaid in the atmosphere, absorbed and released by greenhouse gases.

Without the greenhouse effect, Earth's temperature would be below freezing. It is, in part, a natural process. However, Earth's greenhouse effect is getting stronger as we add greenhouse gases to the atmosphere. That is warming the climate of our planet.

How Does the Greenhouse Effect Work.

Solar energy absorbed at Earth's surface is radiated back into the atmosphere as heat. As the heat makes its way through the atmosphere and back out to space, greenhouse gases absorb much of it. Why do greenhouse gases absorb heat? Greenhouse gases are more complex than other gas molecules in the atmosphere, with a structure that can absorb heat. They radiate the heat back to the Earth's surface, to another greenhouse gas molecule, or out to space.

There are several different types of greenhouse gases. The major ones are carbon dioxide, water vapor, methane, and nitrous oxide. These gas molecules all are made of three or more atoms. The atoms are held together loosely enough that they vibrate

when they absorb heat. Eventually, the vibrating molecules release the radiation, which will likely be absorbed by another greenhouse gas molecule. This process keeps heat near the Earth's surface. Most of the gas in the atmosphere is nitrogen and oxygen, which cannot absorb heat and contribute to the greenhouse effect.

A Couple of Common Greenhouse Gases.

Carbon dioxide: Made of one carbon atom and two oxygen atoms, carbon dioxide molecules make up a small fraction of the atmosphere, but have a large effect on climate. There was about 270 parts per million (ppm) of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere in the mid-19th Century at the start of the Industrial Revolution. The amount is growing as burning fossil fuels releases carbon dioxide into the atmosphere. The concentration has been over 400 ppm since 2015.

Methane: A powerful greenhouse gas, able to absorb far more heat than carbon dioxide, methane is made of one carbon and four hydrogen atoms. It is found in very small quantities in the atmosphere but is able to make a big impact on warming. Methane gas is also used as a fuel. When burned, it releases carbon dioxide greenhouse gas into the atmosphere.

Methane is flammable and is used as a fuel worldwide. It is a principal component of natural gas. Burning methane in the presence of oxygen releases carbon dioxide and water vapor:

Although the concentration of methane in Earth's atmosphere is small (around 1.8 parts per million), it is an important greenhouse gas because it is such a potent heat absorber. The concentration of methane in our atmosphere has risen by about 150% since 1750, apparently largely due to human activities. Methane accounts for about 20% of the heating effects by all of the greenhouse gases combined. Both natural and human sources supply methane to Earth's atmosphere.

Major natural sources of methane include emissions from wetlands and oceans, and from the digestive processes of termites. Sources related to human activities include rice production, landfills, raising cattle and other ruminant animals, and energy generation.

Methane is responsible for around 30% of the rise in global temperatures since the industrial revolution, and rapid and sustained reductions in methane emissions are key to limit near-term warming and improve air quality.

Two key characteristics determine the impact of different greenhouse gases on the climate: the length of time they remain in the atmosphere and their ability to absorb energy. Methane has a much shorter atmospheric lifetime than carbon dioxide (CO₂) – around 12 years compared with centuries – but absorbs much more energy while it exists in the atmosphere.

More Greenhouse Gases = A Warmer Earth.

Even though only a tiny amount of the gases in Earth's atmosphere are greenhouse gases, they have a huge effect on climate. Sometime during this century, the amount of the greenhouse gas carbon dioxide in the atmosphere is expected to double. Other greenhouse gases like methane and nitrous oxide are increasing as well. The quantity of greenhouse gases is increasing as fossil fuels are burned, releasing the gases and other air pollutants into the atmosphere. Greenhouse gases

also make their way to the atmosphere from other sources. Farm animals, for example, release methane gas as they digest food. As cement is made from limestone, it releases carbon dioxide.

With more greenhouse gases in the air, heat passing through on its way out of the atmosphere is more likely to be stopped. The added greenhouse gases absorb the heat. They then radiate this heat. Some of the heat will head away from the Earth, some of it will be absorbed by another greenhouse gas molecule, and some of it will wind up back at the planet's surface again. With more greenhouse gases, heat will stick around, warming the planet.

Atmospheric concentrations of methane are on the rise.

The concentration of methane in the atmosphere is currently around two-and-a-half times greater than its pre-industrial levels. The increase has accelerated in recent years, and preliminary analysis indicates 2021's rise is likely to be amongst the largest ever recorded.

Estimates of methane emissions are subject to a high degree of uncertainty, but the most recent comprehensive assessment – provided in the Global Methane Budget – suggests that annual global methane emissions are around 580 Mt. These includes emissions from natural sources (around 40% of emissions), and the remaining 60% which originate from human activity, known as anthropogenic emissions.

The largest anthropogenic source is agriculture, responsible for around one quarter of emissions, closely followed by the energy sector, which includes emissions from coal, oil, natural gas and biofuels.

Methane affects air quality.

Methane also affects air quality because it can lead to ground level (tropospheric) ozone, a dangerous air pollutant. Methane leaks can also pose explosion hazards.

Current climate change is primarily caused by human emissions of greenhouse gases. This warming can drive large changes in sea level, sea ice and glacier balances, rainfall patterns, and extreme temperatures. This has potentially devastating impacts on human health, farming systems, the stability of societies, and other species.

To limit and stop climate change, we need to greatly reduce global emissions of greenhouse gases. We cover these emissions in our work on CO₂ and other greenhouse gas emissions. This will require massive shifts in our energy and food systems, which we also cover in detail.

On this page, you will find global data and research on the impacts of climate change, including temperature anomalies, sea level rise, sea ice melt, glacier loss, and ocean acidification.

Carbon dioxide concentrations in the atmosphere.

Atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentration is measured in parts per million (ppm). Long-term trends in CO₂ concentrations can be measured at high-resolution using preserved air samples from ice cores.

The world set the goal of keeping the global average temperature rise “well below 2°C” and “pursuing efforts to limit warming to 1.5°C.”

Our global efforts are now measured against these targets of 1.5°C and 2°C. Pathways are assessed on whether they are ‘on track’ to meet these commitments.

Researchers estimate how much more CO₂ we can emit to keep temperatures below 1.5°C and 2°C. This is called the world’s ‘carbon budget’.

How much of our ‘carbon budget’ do we have left to meet these goals?

The chart below shows the remaining carbon budget for 1.5°C and 2°C. These are the latest estimates from Piers Forster and colleagues, published in 2023. <https://ourworldindata.org/how-much-co2-can-the-world-emit-while-keeping-warming-below-15c-and-rc> It’s based on how much can be emitted from the start of 2023 onwards.

There is some uncertainty in how the climate responds to our emissions and the impact of other greenhouse gas emissions, such as methane and nitrous oxide. That means there is not a single ‘budget’. Instead, it is a sliding scale of probabilities. The lower our emissions, the more likely we are to keep temperature rise below our targets.

The budgets, therefore, are given as likelihoods of keeping warming below that level.

For a 5% chance of limiting temperatures to 1.5°C, we could emit a further 250 billion tonnes of CO₂. But there would still be a 50% chance that we go over this target. If we wanted to be risk-averse – and have an 83% chance of staying below – the world can only emit 100 billion tonnes.

Carbon budget to keep global warming below 1.5°C and 2°C.

How much total CO₂ can be emitted to keep global average temperature rise 1.5°C and 2°C, compared to pre-industrial temperatures. This is remaining budget from the start of 2023. Current annual emissions from fossil fuels, industry and land use are shown for context.

What's clear is how small our remaining budget for 1.5°C is.

The world emitted 41 billion tonnes of CO₂ in 2022.² To have a 50% chance of staying below 1.5°C, we can only emit 250 billion tonnes. That's just six years of our current emissions.³

The budget for 2°C is significantly larger. For a 50% chance, the world could emit 1150 billion tonnes. That's around 28 years of current emissions.⁴ For a two-thirds chance, it's 23 years.

That might seem more achievable, but the world is currently not on track to achieve this. Current policies have us on course for around 2.5°C of warming. The world needs to reduce emissions much faster to meet temperatures below 2°C.

The case for methane removal.

The relative concentration of methane has grown more than twice as fast as that of carbon dioxide since the beginning of the Industrial Revolution. Removing methane from the atmosphere could reduce temperatures even faster than carbon dioxide removal alone because methane is 81 times more potent in terms of warming the climate over the first 20 years after its release, and about 27 times more potent over a century. Methane removal also improves air quality by decreasing the concentration of tropospheric ozone, exposure to which causes an estimated one million premature deaths annually worldwide due to respiratory illnesses.

Unlike carbon dioxide, the bulk of methane emissions are human-driven. Primary culprits include agricultural sources such as livestock, which emit methane in their breath and manure, and rice fields, which emit methane when flooded. Waste disposal and fossil fuel extraction also contribute substantial emissions. Natural sources of methane, including soil microbes in wetlands, account for the remaining 40 percent of global methane emissions. They further complicate the picture because some of them, such as thawing permafrost, are projected to increase as the planet warms.

The path to achieving these climate and air quality improvements remains unclear. To focus on this, aspects of carbon dioxide and methane removal are compared and contrasted, a range of methane removal technologies are described, and a framework is outlined for coordinating and accelerating its expansion. This framework will help facilitate more precise analysis of methane removal factors, ranging from site-specific modeling to potential interactions with other climate change mitigation approaches.

Methane is difficult to capture from the air because its concentration is so low, but emerging technologies—such as a class of crystalline materials called zeolites that can absorb the gas—promise a solution, according to researchers. They advocate for increased research into the cost, efficiency, scalability, and energy requirements of these technologies, potential social barriers to their adoption, co-benefits, and possible negative by-products.

Reducing Methane Emissions.

Methane is a potent greenhouse gas with at least 25 times the warming potential of carbon dioxide (CO₂) over a 100-year period. Scientists estimate that methane is responsible for 30% of observed global warming to date and that the level of atmospheric methane continues to rise.

Methane is classified as a short-lived climate pollutant, meaning it stays in the atmosphere for a short time compared to other gases like CO₂. As a result, actions to cut methane emissions will quickly lower their atmospheric concentrations and lead to a relatively quick climate response. Taking action to reduce emissions is one of the fastest, most cost-effective things we can do to fight climate change, protect our environment, and keep our air clean.

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